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**Hope Beyond the Storm: Finding Light Through
Faith and Resilience**

Hope is a force that drives us to do more, keep on fighting, and enhance our patience. This is the kind of force that motivates us to do remarkable things. It is the will to achieve our goal. To have hope is to want an outcome that makes our life better in some way. It will not just help us to be resilient but also can eventually improve our lives because envisioning a better future motivates us to take the steps to make it happen. Whether we think about it or not, hope is a part of everyone's life. Everyone hopes for something. It is an inherent part of being a human. Hope helps us define what we want in our futures, the desires of our hearts, and our deepest secrets.

The definition of hope depends on the person who does the talking. We all have something where we get this so-called hope. When people speak about hope in a spiritual context, it might mean believing good things will happen with faith in the Almighty. They might direct their hopes through their prayers. For others, it might mean to always look on the bright side and see challenges as opportunities to grow and learn. In other words, always hoping for the best. It is indeed a cliché, but it is really true that without the spiritual guidance of God, we are nothing. Whatever the details, hope in general means a desire for things to change for the better, which requires passionate efforts.

Hope serves as the light for many in their dark times. Talking about life, it is full of surprises, which makes it worth living. There are days we experience the gift of life like family, friends, achievements, promotion, or career, and the like, but like everything in this imperfect world, life for sure is naughty and tough. They said life is unfair, but as for me, if life is unfair to everyone, then life is fair. Life lets us experience both the happiest and saddest experiences to learn lessons. Indeed, everything happens for a reason. Good things happen for us to appreciate life.

On the other hand, bad things happen to teach us a lesson that can make us stronger. Experiencing these dark sides of life is a struggle that we need to face. Every day is not always a happy day, so having hope is the light that we need amidst these trying times.

As we move forward, we have a lot of dark sides of life that bother our daily living. Some are still in grief over losing a loved one. Some suffer from illness. There are also some who are struggling financially. Just years ago, we faced this global pandemic, which harmed public health, and today we are facing this global energy crisis, which affects our global economy. We feel a deep sense of uncertainty. We realize how fragile and vulnerable

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we are. It is as if we are suddenly blindsided and brought to a standstill by this pestilence. Unsure of what will happen next, we often take a deep breath to calm our racing pulses. The steep economic downturn and concomitant loss of jobs and incomes, economic distress, and lowered quality of life. None of us was prepared for this outbreak. Some are led to ask why these happen to us. Some have a hard time finding hope if there is an end to this nightmare.

People have different fights to face, but even though it is difficult, there is always light at the end of every tunnel. There is always sun after the rain. We have to focus on looking at the bright side, even in the darkest part of life. Man, in nature is full of hope, with enough resiliency, he can stand from a fall, learn his lessons, and create adaptations and innovations. For instance, in order to gain a wise perspective, we must face our fears. Fears can be healthy or exaggerated, and sometimes paralyzing. It takes wisdom to admit that there are dangers around us that need to be properly and fearfully respected, and it takes wisdom to see through the exaggerations and fearmongering of those who use the pains of others for their benefit. Circumstances change dramatically from day to day, so we must act based on the best information we have. Indeed, all of us must accept the responsibilities we have in our given spheres of influence, such as in the home, work, church, or community, where we are called upon to serve and to lead. We must seek wisdom and make the very best decisions we can as we all endeavor to act generously and selflessly, in ways consistent with all that we believe as followers of Christ, on behalf of others. Moreover, we need to admit to certain specific fears – fears that relate to life and death. Moreover, the fear of having nothing to put on the table for the family is also dominant for most people, if not all. For many people, it is indeed a life-threatening situation, a test of survival. With all that has been said and done, it is better to plan things out so as not to get worse than being caught unprepared.

There is light, there is hope, and God is both our light and hope. He is our shelter during storms and offers His yoke for those who have a heavy burden. God is our savior because everything about the existence of God is hope. He is the way, the truth, and the life. With God, everything is possible if we believe and trust in Him. At the end, everything in this world is temporary, and our permanent shelter is alongside God in His kingdom, so while waiting for that day, let us be hopeful because God is the light in the dark of our lives.